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SiC/SiC COMPOSITES FABRICATED BY ELECTROPHORETIC DEPOSITION COMBINED WITH POLYMER INFILTRATION AND PYROLYSIS PROCESS

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RESEARCH BACKGROUND

- Continuous silicon carbide (SiC) fiber reinforced SiC matrix (SiC/SiC) composites are considered to be the promising candidate materials in aerospace and nuclear fields.
- Composites have a series of excellent properties such as low density, high specific strength, high specific modulus, high temperature resistance, high thermal shock resistance, low radioactivity and high radiation resistance.
- The thermal conductivity of existing SiC/SiC composites are low, especially for the SiC/SiC composites fabricated by Polymer Infiltration and Pyrolysis (PIP) process.
- In order to improve the thermal conductivity of PIP-SiC/SiC composites, the SiC micro-powder was introduced into SiC matrix by using Electrophoretic Deposition (EPD) process, which can increase the crystallinity, density and purity of PIP-SiC/SiC composites.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 Density and porosity of SiC matrix doped with different content of beta-SiC powder

Ratio (wt%)	Density(g/cm ³)	Open porosity (%)
10	1.96	7.77
30	2.03	4.42
50	2.21	2.89
70	2.24	2.20

Table 2 Thermal Conductivity of SiC matrix doped with different content of beta-SiC powder

Ratio (wt%)	Thermal conductivity (W/(m·K))	Thermal diffusion coefficient (mm ² /s)	Specific heat capacity (J/(g·K))
10	0.65	0.736	0.452
30	1.31	1.106	0.582
50	2.04	1.806	0.587
70	2.38	2.288	0.406

- The results show that with the increase of SiC micro-powder content, the sample density increases, the porosity decreases greatly, and the thermal conductivity improves remarkably.
- The thermal conductivity of the samples prepared by doping 70% SiC micro-powder is 2.38 W/(m·K), nearly four times that of the samples prepared by doping 10% SiC micro-powder.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 3 Properties of SiC/SiC composites fabricated by EPD combined with PIP process

Sample	Density (g/cm ³)	Open porosity (%)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Elastic modulus (GPa)	Fracture toughness (MPa·m ^{1/2})	Thermal Conductivity (W/(m·K))
Tradition	2.33	7.7	425±41.7	131±11.1	13.6±1.6	3.22
EPD	2.22	8.3	288±33.7	84.8±10.1	8±1.1	2.3

Fig.1 Stress-displacement curves of SiC/SiC composites fabricated by EPD combined with PIP process

Fig.2 Fracture micrographs of SiC/SiC composites fabricated by EPD combined with PIP process

- The results show that the properties of the SiC/SiC composites prepared by EPD combined with PIP process decreased greatly, compared with the composites without SiC powder in the matrix.
- The density of SiC/SiC composites prepared by EPD combined with PIP process is less than that of composites without SiC powder, and the thermal conductivity of the composites has not achieved the desired results.
- SiC fibers are vulnerable to current damage during electrophoretic deposition, resulting in a decrease in the performance of SiC fibers. The reasons need further analysis in the follow-up work.

Thanks for your attention !

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